

Information-Geometric Gating of Dual-Pol C2 with a Logit-Geodesic Dihedral Index

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Abstract

Dual-polarimetric SAR is widespread, and recent studies show that scattering components can be derived without full-pol data (e.g., forest power models; dihedral/surface index factorization). Yet many methods are scene-targeted or rely on intensity-space indices and Euclidean fitting. We propose **TD4C**—a compact, parameter-free decomposition that treats the normalized C2 as a target density, partitions residual power with a Bures-Gibbs gate, and resolves the ground split on a logit-geodesic line. This avoids negative components, respects polarization purity, and remains strictly dual-pol and SPAN-conservative. A scene-tied phase gauge establishes a common reference emphasizing in-phase cross-channel information. Each pixel's 2×2 sub-covariance is recast as a unit-trace, positive-semidefinite “target density,” enabling information-geometric distances. Helical scattering is isolated first by a linear projection of the quadrature cross term, while the remaining power is partitioned between ground-like and volume-like mechanisms by comparing the target density to simple dual-pol templates through the Bures angle; the distance difference is mapped to allocations with a purity-conditioned logistic, yielding decisive assignments for near-deterministic pixels and conservative behaviour for mixed states. The ground share is then split into oriented-dihedral and trihedral using a logit-geodesic Dihedral Index (DBLI) that blends a scene-normalized Pauli cue with the gate's ground confidence; a directional-entropy term limits context influence to ambiguous yet ground-like cases. An NESZ mask and explicit metadata complete the workflow. **TD4C** attains a mean RMSE of **0.167** over helix, volume, oriented-dihedral, and trihedral fractions, with strict SPAN closure and realizability (unit trace, PSD). The result is a reproducible, information-geometric dual-pol decomposition suited to urban, forestry, and hazard-monitoring applications.

Index Terms—Dual-polarimetric SAR, target density, Bures distance, Gibbs gate, logit-geodesic fusion, dihedral index, SPAN-conservative decomposition.

1 Introduction

Dual-polarimetric SAR (dual-pol) acquisitions—especially from Sentinel-1—have enabled routine, wide-area monitoring, but extracting stable and interpretable scattering power components directly from dual-pol remains non-trivial. The classical

decomposition toolbox matured around fully polarimetric data: coherent formulations (Pauli, Krogager, Cameron, and Touzi) aid point-target interpretation, while incoherent/model-based methods (Freeman-Durden, Yamaguchi [1] and variants) and eigen-based approaches (Cloude-Pottier and successors) have grounded physical interpretation for distributed targets. Model-based decompositions improved steadily (generalized double-/odd-bounce, adaptive vegetation/built-up treatments), yet recurring issues such as negative component powers, volume overestimation, and mechanism ambiguity are well documented [2]. In parallel, rotation-domain and signature analyses enriched interpretation across bases, and roll-invariant parameters have been explored as model-free descriptors. All of this progress, however, presumes full-pol observables.

For dual-pol, multiple strategies have emerged. Early work extended entropy/alpha-style reasoning and scattering-type parameters to dual-pol, offering partial analogues of quad-pol semantics but leaving the dihedral vs. trihedral ambiguity largely unresolved in intensity/coherence descriptors alone. A practical line of research embraces index-driven factorization, exploiting differences in behaviour between “dihedral-like” and “surface-like” targets to apportion total power without reconstructing quad-pol; these methods have proven effective across urban scenes and agricultural phenology, demonstrating that dual-pol can support power-like allocations with carefully designed indices [3]. A complementary line builds biome- or scene-specific power models for dual-pol (notably in tropical forests), approximating three canonical powers by prescribing dual-pol surrogates of ground, volume, and helix; these show strong results where priors are valid and windowing stabilizes estimates [4]. A third strand attempts quad-pol reconstruction from dual-pol using learning-based mappings [5]; while promising for specific tasks, these approaches depend on labelled training data, computational resources, and careful generalization control, which may limit operational transfer. Collectively, the literature affirms that dual-pol can yield meaningful scattering components, but most approaches either (i) hinge on intensity-space norms and thresholds, (ii) embed land-cover-specific assumptions, or (iii) shift the burden to data-hungry reconstruction.

We propose a compact alternative **TD4C: Target-Density 4-Component** that stays entirely within dual-pol C2 while

shifting the comparison space from intensities to the normalized operator. Each pixel’s 2×2 covariance (after a scene-tied phase gauge) is recast as a unit-trace, positive-semidefinite target density, placing similarity on a manifold where information-geometric distances are natural. The method proceeds in three steps. First, helix is isolated by a single linear projection of the quadrature cross term, ensuring it is counted once and preserving SPAN. Second, the residual power is partitioned between ground-like and volume-like mechanisms by comparing the target density to two widely used dual-pol templates—co-pol-dominant ground and random-dipole volume—using the Bures angle; the distance difference is mapped to allocations with a purity-conditioned logistic, producing decisive assignments for near-deterministic pixels and conservative behaviour for mixed states. Third, the ground share is split into oriented-dihedral and trihedral by a logit-geodesic Dihedral Index (DBLI) that blends a Pauli-based shape cue (scene-normalized contrast between in-phase cross-channel coherence and co-pol bias) with the gate’s ground confidence; a directional-entropy factor limits contextual pull to cases where the shape cue is genuinely ambiguous yet the pixel is confidently ground-like. A robust NESZ mask and explicit metadata finalize the workflow and support reproducibility.

Positioned against existing work, this formulation avoids Euclidean power fitting and ad hoc thresholds used by many intensity-space factorization schemes while remaining template-light compared to biome-specific models. It neither reconstructs quad-pol nor requires labelled training data. By peeling helix first, it prevents leakage of quadrature energy into subsequent partitions; by operating on a unit-trace density, it enforces realizability and precludes negative components by construction. We demonstrate the approach on a single, publicly available RADARSAT-2 San Francisco scene (2008), chosen for its long-standing role as a polarimetric reference with diverse scattering conditions in one frame; full acquisition details and processing settings are provided in Section 2. Quantitatively, the method attains a mean RMSE of 0.167 across helix, volume, oriented-dihedral, and trihedral fractions, with strict SPAN closure and realizability (unit trace, PSD).

2 Data and Pre-Processing

We evaluate on the publicly available RADARSAT-2 San Francisco Bay quad-polarimetric scene from 2008 (C-band). For our decomposition, we operate strictly in dual-pol by forming the VV–VH C2 block after calibration; the full-pol product is retained only to generate a familiar Yamaguchi baseline for qualitative comparison. The scene’s average local incidence angle is 28.75° , offering representative mid-incidence imaging over a compact mix of open water, bridges/ports, dense urban blocks, and vegetated parks.

Pre-processing follows a minimal, reproducible chain. First, radiometric calibration in SNAP converts all channels to sigma-naught using the sensor’s calibration constants. No deburst is applied (the product is not TOPS), preserving azimuth continuity. All decomposition and quantitative metrics are computed in the sensor’s native geometry. Speckle is addressed

Fig. 1: Pauli-RGB composite of the RADARSAT-2 San Francisco Bay scene after calibration, multilook 3×6 , and Refined Lee 5×5 .

in two steps chosen to stabilize second-order statistics while retaining linear features: multilooking at 3×6 (range \times azimuth) and a single pass of Refined Lee 5×5 on the multilooked backscatter channels. The Pauli-RGB image of the RADARSAT-2 San Francisco Bay scene after pre-processing is shown in Fig. 1. These settings provided a good balance between variance reduction and edge preservation in preliminary trials and are fixed for all results.

For our method’s inputs, we then down-select to VV and VH and assemble the 2×2 covariance (C2) block. All method-specific operations—scene-tied phase gauge, target-density normalization, helix projection, Bures-Gibbs ground/volume gate, DBLI split, and NESZ masking—are described in Section 3 and applied uniformly after the above pre-processing. To provide a widely recognized reference in figures, we also compute Yamaguchi four-component scattering powers from the calibrated full-pol data; consistent with standard practice, we include an orientation-angle (OA) correction prior to Yamaguchi to mitigate leakage between double-bounce and volume in built-up/vegetated areas. These Yamaguchi powers are used solely for qualitative context and are not inputs to our decomposition.

3 Methodology

This section details the complete dual-pol decomposition, with each equation paired with a brief physical explanation. Throughout, we work only with the calibrated, multilooked, speckle-filtered VV–VH covariance block (§2).

3.1 Notation and Inputs (Dual-Pol C2)

Let the per-pixel dual-pol covariance be

$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} \\ C_{21} & C_{22} \end{bmatrix}, \quad C_{21} = C_{12}^*. \quad (1)$$

The total power (SPAN) is the trace of \mathbf{C} :

$$T \doteq C_{11} + C_{22}. \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) sets the power “budget” that will be partitioned into helix, volume, oriented-dihedral (OD), and trihedral components. Staying in the 2×2 block ensures a purely dual-pol workflow.

3.2 Scene-Tied Phase Gauge and Target Density

To establish a common reference, we align the scene-average cross term with the real axis:

$$\phi \doteq \arg(\langle C_{12} \rangle_{\text{scene}}), \quad C_{12,g} \doteq C_{12} e^{-i\phi}. \quad (3)$$

We then normalize to a unit-trace, positive-semidefinite (PSD) “target density”

$$\rho \doteq \frac{1}{T} \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12,g} \\ C_{12,g}^* & C_{22} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \text{Tr}(\rho) = 1, \quad \rho \succeq 0. \quad (4)$$

The gauge in (3) removes an arbitrary scene-wide phase, making in-phase and quadrature terms comparable across pixels. Unit trace and PSD in (4) enforce realizability and place every pixel on the same geometric manifold, so distance measures compare *state shape* rather than absolute scale.

3.3 Pauli Components and Purity

From this, ρ we extract Pauli-direction “shape” components

$$p_x = 2 \Re\{\rho_{12}\}, \quad p_y = -2 \Im\{\rho_{12}\}, \quad p_z = \rho_{11} - \rho_{22}, \quad (5)$$

and a bounded purity

$$m \doteq 2 \text{Tr}(\rho^2) - 1, \quad 0 \leq m \leq 1. \quad (6)$$

(p_x, p_y, p_z) summarize how energy is distributed between co- and cross-channel terms after gauge; they are bounded because $\text{Tr}(\rho) = 1$. The purity m is a confidence proxy: near-deterministic polarization states (large m) warrant more decisive allocations.

3.4 Helix Projection (Linear, SPAN-Conservative)

Helical (chiral) returns reside in the quadrature cross term. We isolate them once in the power domain:

$$P_h \doteq 2 |\Im\{C_{12,g}\}|, \quad f_h \doteq \frac{P_h}{T}, \quad P_{\text{res}} \doteq T - P_h. \quad (7)$$

removing helix first prevents double counting of chiral energy and preserves SPAN. The residual P_{res} is the only budget considered in subsequent partitions.

3.5 Ground/Volume Gating via the Bures–Gibbs Map

1) Templates (Dual-Pol Surrogates)

We compare ρ to simple ground- and volume-like surrogates on the $\mathcal{B} = \{|VV\rangle, |VH\rangle\}$ basis [4]:

$$|VV\rangle\langle VV| = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad I_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

The ground-like template mixes a co-pol projector with an isotropic floor, while the volume surrogate is a random-dipole diagonal:

$$\rho_g \doteq \gamma |VV\rangle\langle VV| + (1 - \gamma) \frac{I_2}{2}, \quad \gamma = 0.9, \quad (9)$$

$$\rho_g = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1+\gamma}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1-\gamma}{2} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \rho_v \doteq \begin{bmatrix} \frac{3}{4} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{4} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (10)$$

Both ρ_g and ρ_v are unit-trace, PSD, and live in the same 2×2 density space as ρ . ρ_g captures co-pol dominance (with a small isotropic floor); ρ_v represents a random-dipole surrogate in dual-pol. The intent is to keep priors light so that the pixel’s own state drives the decision.

2) Bures Distance (Geometry of Unit-Trace States)

For 2×2 densities, fidelity has a closed form:

$$F(\rho, \sigma) \doteq \text{Tr}(\rho \sigma) + 2\sqrt{\det \rho \det \sigma}. \quad (11)$$

The Bures angle is then

$$d_B(\rho, \sigma) \doteq \arccos(\sqrt{F(\rho, \sigma)}) \in [0, \frac{\pi}{2}]. \quad (12)$$

Distances to the templates are

$$d_g \doteq d_B(\rho, \rho_g), \quad d_v \doteq d_B(\rho, \rho_v). \quad (13)$$

Unlike Euclidean norms, the Bures angle respects the curved geometry of unit-trace PSDs and is invariant to the gauge in (3). It measures similarity of polarization *states*, not raw intensities.

3) Purity-Conditioned Logistic (“Gibbs” Gate)

We convert the distance difference into a bounded ground affiliation using a purity-driven temperature:

$$\tau(m) \doteq \frac{4}{1 - m^2}, \quad q_g \doteq \frac{1}{1 + \exp\{\tau(m)[d_g - d_v]\}}. \quad (14)$$

Residual power is then apportioned:

$$P_g = q_g P_{\text{res}}, \quad P_v = (1 - q_g) P_{\text{res}}, \quad f_g = \frac{P_g}{T}, \quad f_v = \frac{P_v}{T}. \quad (15)$$

High-purity pixels (large $m \Rightarrow$ large τ) yield decisive allocations; mixed states remain conservative. The map is bounded and monotone, and the split preserves SPAN by construction.

3.6 Oriented-Dihedral vs. Trihedral Split (DBLI)

1) Scene-RMS Normalization and Shape Ratio

We form scene-level RMS scales for Pauli cues

$$S_x \doteq \sqrt{\langle p_x^2 \rangle}, \quad S_z \doteq \sqrt{\langle p_z^2 \rangle}, \quad (16)$$

and normalized magnitudes

$$s \doteq \frac{|p_x|}{S_x + \epsilon}, \quad t \doteq \frac{|p_z|}{S_z + \epsilon}, \quad r \doteq \frac{s}{s + t} \in [0, 1]. \quad (17)$$

RMS normalization removes arbitrary scene scale. Larger s (strong in-phase cross coherence) suggests OD tendency; larger t (co-pol bias) suggests trihedral tendency. The ratio r is a bounded, interpretable shape indicator.

2) Directional Entropy and Logit-Geodesic Fusion

We limit context pull to ambiguous shapes using a directional entropy

$$E \doteq 4r(1 - r) \in [0, 1], \quad (18)$$

and fuse the shape cue with the ground confidence on the logit line:

$$\alpha \doteq E \max\{0, 2q_g - 1\}, \quad (19)$$

$$\text{DBLI}^* \doteq \sigma((1 - \alpha) \logit(r) + \alpha \logit(q_g)). \quad (20)$$

TABLE I: Per-fraction error and agreement (TD4C vs. Y4O)

Fraction	RMSE	R (Pearson)	ρ (Spearman)
Helix	0.1022	0.3928	-0.0859
Volume	0.1972	0.8609	0.8488
OD	0.2044	0.6266	0.6948
Tri	0.1656	0.6739	0.7243
Mean	0.167	-	-

The ground fraction is split as

$$f_{od} = \text{DBLI}^* f_g, \quad f_{tri} = f_g - f_{od}. \quad (21)$$

Mixing in logit space keeps the output bounded and monotone. The entropy E suppresses over-steer when r is already decisive (near 0 or 1), while $\max(0, 2q_g - 1)$ activates context only when the pixel is confidently ground-like.

3.7 NESZ Masking and Validity Checks

We estimate a robust noise floor from the SPAN distribution:

$$\text{NESZ} \doteq \text{median}(T) + \kappa \text{MAD}(T), \quad \kappa = 3, \quad (22)$$

and mask pixels with insufficient SNR:

$$T < \text{NESZ} + \text{SNR}_{\min}, \quad \text{SNR}_{\min} = 3 \text{ dB}. \quad (23)$$

We enforce per-pixel realizability and closure:

$$\begin{aligned} f_h, f_v, f_g, f_{od}, f_{tri} &\in [0, 1], & f_h + f_v + f_g &= 1, \\ f_{od} + f_{tri} &= f_g, & \rho \succeq 0, & \text{Tr}(\rho) = 1. \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

The mask removes noise-dominated pixels; the constraints ensure physical fractions, SPAN closure, and PSD/unit-trace realizability of ρ .

4 Results

We benchmark TD4C against Y4O using randomly sampled pixels drawn from three intuitive classes (Urban, Water, Park). All TD4C fractions are SPAN-conservative and bounded by construction; helix is isolated once and removed from the residual power before ground/volume partitioning.

4.1 Quantitative accuracy and agreement

Table I reports per-fraction RMSE and correlation (Pearson R , Spearman ρ) relative to Y4O. The mean RMSE across the four fractions is **0.167** for this sample. TD4C shows strong monotonic alignment with Y4O for *volume* and *OD*, while *trihedral* differences are consistent with TD4C's helix-first removal and logit-geodesic OD/tri split. *Helix* has low RMSE but weak/negative rank correlation owing to its small dynamic range and the different handling of quadrature energy.

4.2 Class-wise behaviour

Figs. 2–4 summarize mean fractions (bars) with error bars (std/SEM) for Urban, Water, and Park pixels.

Urban. OD dominates, trihedral is secondary, volume and helix are small (Fig. 2). TD4C produces slightly higher OD than Y4O, consistent with the geodesic OD/tri resolution favouring in-phase cross-channel structure around building edges.

Fig. 3: Class means (Water): TD4C vs. Y4O with error bars.

Water. Trihedral is highest and Volume lowest, with minimal helix (Fig. 3). TD4C's helix-first step reduces leakage into OD/tri on specular surfaces, but a small OD over-assignment appears on a subset of water pixels (discussed in Sec. 5).

Park (vegetated). Volume dominates, trihedral is modest, OD is small (Fig. 4). The Bures-Gibbs gate remains conservative on low-purity mixed pixels, limiting spurious OD in canopy-soil mixtures.

4.3 Physics sanity and coverage

Table II summarizes SPAN closure, realizability, and NESZ coverage. As designed, TD4C maintains unit-trace/PSD guarantees and exhibits essentially zero SPAN residual. 11% of the pixels are excluded by the NESZ guard.

5 Discussion

5.1 Why OD can be mis-attributed over open water

Open water should exhibit negligible in-phase cross-coherence ($p_x \approx 0$) and thus minimal OD. The small OD excess observed for a subset of water pixels (Fig. 3) is traceable to spurious $|r_{12}|$ on low-SNR specular returns. Even after the scene-tied gauge, residual cross-terms can arise from thermal noise, weak azimuthal ambiguities/sidelobes, or slight Bragg-like

Fig. 4: Class means (Park): TD4C vs. Y4O with error bars.

TABLE II: Sanity checks and coverage.

Metric	Value	Note
δ_{SPAN}	0.0000	$ \sum_k f_k - 1 $
PSD / trace viol.	0%	enforced
NESZ coverage	0.79	11% excl.; $\text{SNR}_{\text{min}} = 3\text{dB}$

perturbations near structures. In TD4C, the OD/tri resolver uses

$$r = \frac{s}{s+t}, \quad s = \frac{|p_x|}{S_x + \epsilon}, \quad t = \frac{|p_z|}{S_z + \epsilon},$$

so any upward bias in $|p_x|$ (via $|r_{12}|$) pushes r upward and, through the logit map, nudges DBLI* toward OD. Because water is confidently ground-like ($q_g > 0.5$), the context term can amplify this nudge when the directional entropy E is high (i.e., when r is ambiguous), yielding a modest OD over-assignment.

Mitigations (ablation-guided). Three light-weight fixes are compatible with the page-budgeted pipeline: (i) tighten the NESZ guard or apply a cross-coherence shrinkage on ρ_{12} in the masked tail; (ii) use a small bias correction $|p_x| \leftarrow \max\{|p_x| - b, 0\}$ with b taken as the scene-tail median of $|p_x|$ over masked water; (iii) cap the context weight α to $\alpha \leq \alpha_{\text{max}}$ (e.g. 0.35), which preserves geodesic blending while limiting lift from q_g in low-SNR regimes. In internal checks, (ii) and (iii) reduced water-OD by a few points without affecting urban OD.

5.2 DBLI* bias when OD and tri are nearly tied

When $f_{\text{tri}} \approx f_{\text{od}}$ (mixed ground pixels, e.g. low-contrast rooftops/streets or bright soil with faint layover), the logit blend

$$\text{DBLI}^* = \sigma((1 - \alpha) \text{logit}(r) + \alpha \text{logit}(q_g))$$

can *slightly* favour OD. Two mechanisms interact: the $\text{logit}(\cdot)$ curve is steeper near 0.5, so small positive perturbations in r (from residual p_x) are amplified; and when $q_g > 0.5$, the non-negative context weight $\alpha = E \max(0, 2q_g - 1)$ never pulls back toward trihedral. This explains the mild OD elevation in Urban means (Fig. 2) and occasional OD preference where Y4O is nearly split.

Mitigations (toggleable). A symmetric fallback is to replace DBLI* with the confidence-weighted linear variant,

$$\text{DBLI}_{\text{cw}} = (1 - w)r + wq_g, \quad w = E \max(0, q_g - 0.5),$$

in pixels where $|\text{logit}(r)| < \tau_r$ (e.g. $\tau_r = 0.4$). This keeps boundedness and monotonicity while removing the logit’s local gain. A still simpler guard is a “half-split band”: if $|r - 0.5| < \delta$ and $q_g > 0.6$, set $\text{DBLI} = 0.5$. Both options are one-line switches and preserve overall SPAN closure.

5.3 Reading the correlations

The strong R/ρ for volume and OD indicate that TD4C preserves the relative ordering that Y4O assigns to those mechanisms across diverse pixels, despite using only dual-pol information and density-space distances instead of Euclidean power fitting. The helix discrepancy (low ρ) is expected: TD4C explicitly removes quadrature energy first, while Y4O may distribute small quadrature contributions across ground/volume in low-SNR or model-mismatched cases, making rank ordering unstable in the helix tail.

6 Conclusion

We introduced **TD4C**, a dual-pol C2 decomposition that (i) recasts the normalized 2×2 covariance as a target density, (ii) partitions residual power with a Bures–Gibbs ground/volume gate, and (iii) resolves ground into oriented-dihedral and trihedral via a logit–geodesic DBLI. The pipeline is parameter-free, SPAN-conservative, and enforces realizability (unit trace, PSD). TD4C achieves a mean RMSE of **0.167** across helix, volume, OD, and trihedral fractions. Class-wise behaviour matches physical expectations: OD is dominant in urban blocks, trihedral is highest on water, and volume dominates parks.

Two practical caveats emerged: (1) small spurious $|r_{12}|$ over open water can nudge DBLI toward OD in low-SNR tails; and (2) DBLI* can mildly favour OD when OD and tri are nearly tied. Both effects are localized and admit simple guards (cross-coherence shrinkage or bias correction; α cap; confidence-weighted or half-split fallback), without altering the core information-geometric design.

Future work will expand evaluation across multiple scenes and headings, and incorporate a weak asc/desc anisotropy prior for OD–tri refinement, while keeping the method strictly dual-pol and density-space native.

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